

Onto the internal strain self-sensing properties of single walled carbon nanotube-reinforced epoxies

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SUMMARY

Strain self-sensing capabilities of single walled carbon nanotube-epoxy nanocomposites were explored by global and local methods during curing and under mechanical load. Raman tests show that residual compressive strains owed to post-cure thermal contraction exist on the nanocomposite interface and promote an efficient load transfer to the nanotubes.

Keywords: carbon nanotubes, stress sensing, curing process, Raman spectroscopy

ABSTRACT

Non destructive, real-time monitoring of the stress/strain state of polymer composites can be achieved through a “nanomodification” of the matrix. Due to their high Raman scattering, electrical conductivity and implicit sensitivity to pressure and temperature, single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) are ideal elements to fulfil this task. In this work, SWCNT at a loading fraction as low as 0.1 wt% were homogeneously dispersed in a hot-curing epoxy matrix via a three-roll-mill process. Evolution of internal strains resulting alone from the manufacturing process was characterised by *in situ* monitoring of the Raman shifts during the different stages of the curing cycle. The G'-band shift and change in electrical resistance of the cured material was further analyzed under mechanical strain to estimate the magnitude of the internal stress field as well as the reinforcing effect of the SWCNT itself.

INTRODUCTION

Given the unmatched mechanical strength and high aspect ratio of carbon nanotubes (CNT), even substantially small amounts of these could yield tremendous enhancements of the mechanical properties of polymer composites [1]. However, due to the difficulties to individually disperse CNT, this potential benefit has not yet been attained. A more realistic near term application of CNT concerns their use as internal stress and damage sensors in structural materials. Several researchers have studied the “piezoresistivity” properties of CNT-polymer composites [2-4], which are due to

disruption or rearrangement of the CNT conductive network under progressing stress conditions [5-6]. On the other hand, studies of the local response of (single-walled) carbon nanotubes to mechanical stress transferred from a polymer medium provide fundamental insight on the interfacial interaction and thereby load transfer of this kind of materials. Particularly, Raman spectroscopy has been successfully used to characterise the effects of molecular pressure, heating and mechanical deformation of carbon nanotubes within polymer matrices [7-9]. The high Raman scattering of SWCNT and sensitivity of their phonon modes to “environmental” conditions have also been exploited to monitor the evolution of internal strains due to the curing process of thermoset materials [10-11]. Amongst the advantages of Raman spectroscopy as a “stress sensing” technique are its high resolution and simplicity of sample preparation. Additionally, Raman scattering can be used in parallel with other real time techniques such as impedance spectroscopy to yield complementary information upon bulk and local nanotube response to different strain conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Materials and sample preparation

A hot curing system based on the epoxy/amino chemistry (Hunstman Araldite LY564 / Aradur 2954) was used in combination with HiPco single-walled CNT (purchased from Unidym) at a concentration of 0.1 wt%. The nanotubes were dispersed in the epoxy resin with the use of a three roll mill. Then, the hardener was added under mechanical stir, and the mixture was evacuated shortly to eliminate air. Part of this preparation was reserved for the *in situ* curing experiments, while the rest was cast on aluminium moulds and cured with the standard cycle (1 hr at 80°C + 8 hrs at 140 °C) to produce the specimens for mechanical tests.

In situ experiments

A Jobin Yvon HR800 Raman spectrometer with the 633 nm He-Ne laser line and a 50x long working distance objective were used. A heating stage (Linkam THMS600) was placed underneath the microscope to adjust the curing temperatures. For the specimens, a thin layer (~100 µm) of the CNT/epoxy mixture was deposited on a glass substrate. Additional information on the curing behaviour of the sample was obtained through DSC, parallel plates rheometry, and laser dilatometry [12].

Bending tests

Four point bending tests were carried out (University of Manchester) under Raman observation with the use of a Renishaw Raman spectrometer equipped with the same type of laser and objective as in the *in situ* experiments. A self-made bending rig was used in combination with strain gages to adjust the desired strain steps, either in compression or in tension mode. Rectangular specimens with dimensions 10x6x3 mm were used. Electrical resistance of the sample was measured with the use of a multimeter (Keithley 6512) contacted with the sample by means of silver paint contacts attached to the sample’s surface.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In situ curing

A Raman time mapping of the curing cycle of the nanocomposite is shown in Figure 1. The dominant role of temperature is evidenced by the instantaneous decrease of the G'-band position at each isothermal interval (cure/post-cure). The shift is more pronounced in the very first minutes of both processes, due to a sudden rise of the resin's temperature as a result of the exothermic heat released once the reaction is started. As crosslinking progresses, the G'-band position trends to higher frequencies since compressive (shrinkage) forces start to compete with thermal expansion. A saturation point is reached after approximately 2 hours of postcure at 140 °C, indicating that at this point, the crosslinking reaction was completed, or that any changes in the nanocomposite microstructure are too small to be detected. Upon cooling a further, significantly larger, positive shift results from thermal shrinkage.

Figure 1. Raman (G'-band) shifts during curing cycle of the nanocomposite: at room temperature RT (before curing), during curing at 80°C and post-curing at 140°C, and finally, at room temperature after cooling down from the last temperature step.

In Figure 2, a close up to the curing interval at 80 °C (here extended to 3 hours) of the Raman in situ curve is presented together with the corresponding volumetric shrinkage and glass temperature evolution curves. Although the two latter measurements concern explicitly resin behaviour, all three curves display similar exponential growth since they all depend on the formation of covalent bonds throughout the matrix resin. Past the vitrification point ($T_g = T_{cure}$), the resin has practically reached its maximum shrinkage level, however the Raman shift still rises because residual stresses are created by continuing to cure at a temperature below the new T_g . It is worth to notice that although chemical crosslinking reduces the resin volume by almost 6% (in contrast, thermal shrinkage of the fully cured nanocomposite is known to be <1%), it does not lead to such a pronounced Raman shift as the one observed at the end of the cooling step. This could be explained in terms of the modulus of elasticity of the nanocomposite. The higher the modulus of the cured resin becomes, the more efficiently it can “transfer” stress to the nanotubes.

Even at the gel point, when the storage (elastic) modulus of the epoxy has nearly reached its maximum value, stress can still be relaxed because $T_{\text{cure}} > T_g$. The most critical condition for stress transfer is therefore reached at the vitrification point, since it implies a high elastic modulus and hindered relaxation of the macromolecule. Since for the epoxy system chosen, vitrification is reached already at an advanced degree of cure (>0.9), only small compressive strains develop till the endpoint of the reaction.

Figure 2. Shrinkage, Raman shift and T_g evolution curves during curing at 80 °C

To prevent overestimation of the Raman shift attributed to thermal contraction, a component merely due to heating effects on the SWCNT has to be taken into account. In Figure 3, the G'-band position is plotted vs. temperature for the pure nanotubes and the SWCNT-epoxy cured sample. In the latter case, an inflection point occurs at T_g , after which only a slight dependence on temperature is observed. Since stress can be relaxed when $T > T_g$, the shift rate on this region is considered to be the Raman temperature dependence of SWCNT in the polymer matrix, as discussed in [11].

Figure 3. Temperature dependence of Raman G'-band for HiPCO single-walled carbon nanotubes and the SWCNT-epoxy nanocomposite

Mechanical deformation

A typical curve obtained during the bending tests of the SWCNT-epoxy nanocomposite is presented in Figure 4. Compressive test were performed at low strain percentages (<1%) to prevent damage of the sample. Subsequent tensile tests were carried out till sample failure. The higher shift rate observed under tensile mode (in the elastic region) than under compressive mode is most likely due to the presence of residual compressive strains in the SWCNT-epoxy interface, which are introduced by thermal contraction of the resin as it cools down from its last processing temperature. The inset on the graphic shows the corresponding G'-band shift with thermal strain (calculated with the thermal expansion coefficient of the nanocomposite and the corresponding temperature intervals from Figure 3). The shift rate per 1% of thermal strain is significantly higher than that of surface strain (either tensile or compressive) since the first can be considered a case analogous to isotropic compression/expansion, which involves a much higher interfacial interaction of the nanotubes and the epoxy resin. Thus, SWCNT respond with different sensitivities to different matrix deformation conditions.

Also, the calibration plot of Raman shift vs. tensile strain shows an inflection point at around 1.5% surface strain, which is most likely due to the onset of plastic deformation of the nanocomposite. Therefore, the local response of SWCNT to applied strain mirrors the changes occurring on the matrix until the endpoint of the test, which might be due to the existence of a strong bonding interface.

Figure 4. Raman curves obtained during compressive and tensile loads in a 4-point bending test. The inset displays the corresponding Raman shift rate upon to thermal contraction/expansion of the fully cured nanocomposite.

Due to the extensive shear work attained with the three-roll-mill, a very good dispersion of the nanotubes was achieved despite the strong intermolecular forces holding the SWCNT agglomerates together. As a result, a highly homogeneous nanocomposite material was produced, which is evidenced by the small error bars on the Raman vs. strain plots (accounting for 5 measurements per each strain step). Therefore, the calibration curve in Figure 4 is considered to be representative for every point of the specimen, neglecting those of layers which were in direct contact with the moulds.

To correlate the local SWCNT response to applied strain with those changes occurring at the network level, electrical conductivity measurements were carried out in parallel to the Raman experiments (Figure 5). Under tensile mode, a continuous increase of resistance is observed in the elastic region. However, the curve of the resistance change vs. strain includes a contribution of compressive stress originated on the bottom of the sample, and thereby deviates from the purely exponential growth reported in [3] and [4]. At a strain of $\sim 1.5\%$ (plastic deformation), the instrument lost sensitivity to the high resistance attained by the sample, and any measurements after this point are therefore out of range. It is important to note that although both sensing techniques require a good dispersion of the nanotubes in the matrix, the definition of this requirement differs significantly for each one of them. While high homogeneity (similar dispersion patterns for every microscopic spot) yield more reliable Raman measurements, a certain degree of agglomeration is necessary to build up the CNT conductive network, and thereby display the piezoresistant effect.

Figure 5. Raman shift and electrical resistance changes during 4-point-bending tension

CONCLUSIONS

The sensitivity of single walled carbon nanotubes to strain and temperature, in combination with their optical and electrical properties enable the utilisation of this material as internal stress/strain sensor in polymer materials. In this work, the Raman response of SWCNT-epoxy nanocomposites was studied under different strain scenarios: curing, thermal expansion and surface strain.

From the curing experiments, it could be concluded that only small strain levels develop as a result of the crosslinking process, as long as the elastic modulus of the nanocomposite is significantly lower than its final value (i.e. before gelation point) and vitrification of the material is overcome with a postcure step, stress can be relaxed around the CNT-epoxy interface.

On the other hand, compressive residual strains present on the fully cured sample are mainly due to thermal shrinkage of the cured material. The presence of these thermal residual strains leads to different responses of the SWCNT while strained under tensile or compression mode, and might also strengthen the interface with the epoxy resin, favouring a more efficient load transfer mechanism. Indeed, during the bending tests no interfacial failure could be detected under Raman analysis, and the nanotube behaviour reflected that of the matrix as the strain level increased.

The local response of SWCNT under mechanical deformation can yield complementary information upon the global response of the conductive network by a combination of Raman spectroscopy with electrical resistivity/conductivity

measurements. However, a compromise of good dispersion degree and sample homogeneity and a filler concentration sufficiently high to reduce the distance between neighbouring CNTs must exist to ensure statistical accuracy.

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REFERENCES

1. Thostenson ET, Ren Z, Chou TW. Advances in the science and technology of carbon nanotube and their composites: a review. *Composites Science and Technology* 2001;61:1899-912.
2. Li CY, Chou TW. Strain and pressure sensing using single-walled carbon nanotubes. *Nanotechnology* 2004;15(11):1493-6.
3. Böger L, Wichmann MHG, Meyer LO, Schulte K. Load and health monitoring in glass fibre reinforced composites with an electrically conductive nanocomposite epoxy matrix. *Composites Science and Technology* 2008;68:1886-94.
4. Wichmann MHG, Buschhorn ST, Böger L, Adelung R, Schulte K. Direction sensitive bending sensors based on multi-wall carbon nanotube/epoxy nanocomposites. *Nanotechnology* 2008;19:475503.1-5.
5. Fiedler B, Gojny FH, Wichmann MHG, Bauhofer W, Schulte K. Can carbon nanotubes be used to sense damage in composites? *Annales des Chimie, Science des Matériau* 2004; 29(6): 81-94.
6. Thostenson ET, Chou TW. Carbon nanotube networks: sensing of distributed strain and damage for life prediction and self healing. *Advanced Materials* 2006;18:2837-41.
7. Wood JR, Wagner HD. Single-wall carbon nanotubes as molecular pressure sensors. *Applied Physics Letters* 2000;76(20):2883-5.
8. Cooper CA, Young RJ, Halsall M. Investigation into the deformation of carbon nanotubes and their composites through the use of Raman spectroscopy. *Composites Part A*, 2001;32:401-11.
9. Cao CC, Young RJ. A Raman spectroscopic investigation of heating effects and the deformation behaviour of epoxy/SWNT composites. *Composites Science and Technology* 2004;64:2291-5.
10. de la Vega A, Kovacs JZ, Bauhofer W, Schulte K. Combined Raman and dielectric spectroscopy on the curing behaviour and stress build up of carbon nanotube-epoxy composites. *Composites Science and Technology* 2008 (in press; available online).

11. de la Vega A, de Almeida Prado LA, Kovacs JZ, Bauhofer W, Schulte K. SWCNT as cure-induced stress sensors in epoxy nanocomposites. *Solid State Phenomena* 2009;151:48-53.
12. Holst M, Schänzlin K, Wenzel M, Xu J, Lellinger D, Alig I. Time-resolved method for the measurement of volume changes during polymerization. *Journal of Polymer Science: Part B* 2004;43:2314-25.